

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
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IMPROVING ADHERENCE TO BRAIN TRAUMA FOUNDATION GUIDELINES
ON INTRACRANIAL PRESSURE MONITORING AND
CEREBROSPINAL FLUID DRAINAGE

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Traumatic brain injury is the third leading cause of injury-related deaths. Although the Brain Trauma Foundation (BTF) established guidelines in 1995, adherence to these practice recommendations has not been consistent. ICP monitoring and CSF drainage are two of these guidelines that are explored in this quality improvement project.

The purpose of this DNP project was to increase adherence to the BTF guidelines for ICP monitoring and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) drainage during the first 24 hours after external ventricular drain (EVD) placement in adult patients with severe TBI (sTBI). The objectives of this project were to (a) describe baseline adherence rates to the BTF guidelines for ICP monitoring and CSF drainage, (b) implement the SIBICC algorithm and a CSF drainage protocol, (c) develop and implement an educational program regarding the SIBICC algorithm and the CSF drainage protocol, (d) evaluate adherence rates to the BTF guidelines for ICP monitoring and CSF drainage after implementation, (e) increase knowledge related to BTF guidelines on ICP monitoring and CSF drainage, and (f) increase self-efficacy (confidence) on ICP monitoring and CSF drainage. The Plan-Do-Study-Act was the conceptual framework used to support this quality improvement project. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, implementation was suspended until normal hospital operations are resumed.

Data from a convenience sample of six sTBI patients meeting inclusion criteria and exclusion criteria during pre-implementation were collected. The average

completeness of documentation for ICP monitoring and CSF drainage was 83% and 65.3% respectively. Adherence rates for ICP monitoring were 33% and 0% for CSF drainage. Nurses' knowledge scores of ICP monitoring and CSF drainage increased after education (from an average of 55.6% pre-test to 80% post-test, with a 26.6 percentage point improvement). Nurses' self-efficacy for ICP monitoring and CSF drainage also improved (from 12% to 17% for the highly confident item for ICP monitoring, and from 7% to 20% highly confident for CSF drainage).

Although an improvement in adherence rate was not determined within the project timeframe, analysis of baseline data revealed areas for improvement. Variation in practice was shown to exist on ICP monitoring and CSF drainage and is expected to be reduced and eventually replaced by evidence-based guidelines with the future implementation of the SIBICC algorithm and the CSF drainage protocol.

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BACKGROUND

Traumatic brain injury (TBI) remains a significant healthcare issue in the United States (US) and is the third leading cause of injury-related deaths. According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC, 2019), TBIs caused 56,800 deaths, with 2,529 deaths occurring among children. In addition to mortality, TBIs are associated with disabilities which affect patients' quality of life and disrupt their families. In 2010, the direct and indirect medical costs associated with TBIs were estimated at \$76.5 billion (CDC, 2017).

In 1995, the Brain Trauma Foundation (BTF) surveyed 270 trauma centers which revealed significant variation in the management of severe head injury. As a result, the BTF, in collaboration with the American Association of Neurological Surgeons, developed *Guidelines for the Management of Severe Head Injury*. Revisions of these evidence-based guidelines occurred in 2000, 2007, and 2016 (BTF, 2016). Despite these multiple revisions to improve the guidelines, due to practicality, they are difficult to implement in the clinical setting. The BTF guidelines were not designed in a protocol format that is systematic and practical for clinicians to use in different practice settings.

In 2019, the Seattle International Severe Traumatic Brain Injury Consensus Conference (SIBICC) workgroup composed of 42 clinically active TBI specialists developed an evidence-based management algorithm for sTBI, known as the SIBICC algorithm (Hawryluk et al., 2019). The SIBICC task force used the fourth edition of the BTF guidelines as their reference in the development of the SIBICC algorithm. The SIBICC algorithm reorganized the BTF guidelines into a user-friendly format. Concepts

were operationalized leading to improved clinical applicability and utility of the BTF guidelines.

The overall adherence rate to BTF guidelines is highly variable (ranging from 0 to 100%) with a median adherence rate of only 60.7% (Khormi et al., 2018). Gupta et al. (2016) reported that BTF guideline adherence rates of less than 65% were significantly associated with a two-fold increase in inpatient hospital mortality. In contrast, following BTF guidelines was associated with improved patient outcomes. In the study conducted by Gupta et al. (2016), an increase in guideline adherence rate by 1% was associated with a 3% lower in-hospital mortality rate. Similar results were illustrated at San Francisco General Hospital (SFGH), an urban Level 1 trauma center. The 24-hour mortality rate for sTBI patients at SFGH dropped by 59% with adoption of the BTF guidelines (Tarapore et al., 2015).

Purpose Statement

Therefore, the purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to increase adherence to the BTF guidelines for ICP monitoring and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) drainage during the first 24 hours after external ventricular drain (EVD) placement in adult patients with sTBI in an urban Level 1 trauma center in Southern California. The objectives of this project were to (a) describe baseline adherence rates to the BTF guidelines for ICP monitoring and CSF drainage during the first 24 hours after EVD placement in a sample of six adult sTBI patients, (b) develop and implement ICP monitoring and CSF drainage guidelines (later identified in the SIBICC algorithm and incorporated in the CSF drainage protocol), (c) develop and implement an educational program regarding the SIBICC algorithm and the CSF drainage protocol for ICP

management, (d) evaluate adherence rates to the BTF guidelines for ICP monitoring and CSF drainage after implementation of the SIBICC algorithm and the CSF drainage protocol in a similar sample of six patients with sTBI, (e) increase knowledge related to BTF guidelines on ICP monitoring and CSF drainage, and (f) increase self-efficacy (confidence) on ICP monitoring and CSF drainage.

Because the COVID-19 pandemic emerged during the developmental phase of this project, implementation of the SIBICC algorithm and CSF drainage protocol had to be postponed. Therefore, this paper addresses the steps taken prior to the implementation and evaluation of the algorithm and protocol effectiveness.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework used for this project was the Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) cycle. The PDSA cycle is used for evaluating a change within an organization. The PDSA cycle was developed by the Institute for Healthcare Improvement and can be used for “organizing learning, testing, and implementing” of a doctoral project (Langley et al., 2009, p. 411). The PDSA cycle allows for multiple iterations of implementing an intervention in order to determine its effectiveness.

Plan

The PDSA cycle begins with the Plan stage. During the Plan stage, the objectives of the project are developed, questions are formulated and predictions to questions are generated. The plan describes the who, what, where and when of the project. It includes a data collection plan for gathering information (Langley et al., 2009). For this project, an extensive literature review was conducted related to the BTF guidelines, SIBICC algorithm, and identified barriers and enablers to guideline adherence specific to ICP

monitoring and CSF drainage. A focused review of literature on CSF studies was also undertaken to guide the development of the CSF drainage protocol.

Key stakeholders provided clinical and administrative support for the project. The key stakeholders included department leaders from trauma, neurosurgery, and nursing who worked collaboratively to ensure that the project objectives and outcomes aligned with departmental goals and priorities. Buy-in from all key stakeholders was critical to the success of this project. Buy-in was established through multiple meetings in which the need for the project was discussed. The project author together with the trauma and neurosurgery attending physicians will implement the project and evaluate its effectiveness at a later date and continue to serve as the *champions*, who are described as individuals who “rally around a cause and keep it in the consciousness of practitioners until it becomes a hardwired practice change” (Proehl & Hoyt, 2014, p. 207).

Do

The Do stage involved providing the education component of the project. The project author provided the education regarding the SIBICC algorithm and the CSF drainage protocol to the intensive care unit (ICU) nursing staff. Designated neurosurgeons and trauma surgeons were to provide physician education during one of their routine educational meetings. The educational program was 30 minutes long and offered in multiple sessions at designated classrooms (see Appendix A). Education consisted of a didactic class and included background information on traumatic brain injury and the BTF guidelines, and the SIBICC algorithm (see Appendices B & C). The components of the SIBICC algorithm and the CSF drainage protocol were explained in detail (see Appendices D-H). The education session concluded with a case study to

facilitate application of learned concepts and a question and answer section to achieve learning outcomes in the cognitive and affective domains (see Appendix I).

Upon completion of training and when normal hospital operations resume after COVID-19 is no longer a significant operational concern, the SIBICC algorithm and the CSF drainage protocol will be implemented. Visual reminders in the form of laminated sheets containing information regarding the SIBICC algorithm and CSF drainage protocol will be posted in strategic locations where they would be easily visible, such as the education boards and the resource binders commonly used for quick reference, upon official roll-out of the SIBICC algorithm and CSF drainage protocol. Posters will be displayed in the unit in areas commonly frequented by staff to reinforce learning.

Study

According to Langley et al. (2009), this stage of the cycle involves a complete analysis of data, comparison of data to predictions, and summary of lessons learned. Convenience sampling identified the first six patients meeting inclusion and exclusion criteria for pre-implementation analysis. Data on documentation of ICP monitoring and CSF drainage were collected, together with other clinical and demographic data. Analyzed pre-implementation data consisted of completeness of documentation, adherence rates, and self-efficacy for both ICP monitoring and CSF drainage. Post-implementation data will be collected when the project is cleared by administration to resume. Data before and after implementation will then be compared. Knowledge of the CSF drainage protocol and BTF guidelines related to ICP monitoring pre- and post-education were also assessed and analyzed.

Act

In this stage of the cycle, changes in the process to be made for the next improvement cycle are identified (Langley et al., 2009). The project author plans to obtain feedback from physician champions and ICU nurses as part of the quality improvement process. Reeducation of staff as well as updating the electronic medical record system are potential changes for the future.

In conclusion, the author selected the PDSA cycle as the conceptual framework to assist in providing the appropriate structure and to guide or navigate towards the completion of this project. The project's PDSA cycle is illustrated in a diagram (Figure 1) to highlight the different components.

Figure 1. PDSA cycle showing the different tasks corresponding to each of the four components of the cycle.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The purpose of this DNP project is to increase adherence to the BTF guidelines on ICP monitoring and CSF drainage. The author conducted a comprehensive literature review that covered the major topics of ICP monitoring and management using the following search terms: severe traumatic brain injury, adherence to BTF guidelines, ICP monitoring, ICP management, high ICP reduction treatments, high ICP interventions, cerebral perfusion pressure, head elevation, mannitol, hypertonic saline, neuromuscular blockers (NMB), barbiturate coma, cerebrospinal fluid drainage, and targeted temperature management. The following databases were searched: PubMed, CINAHL Plus with Full-Text (EBSCO), Science Direct, and Cochrane Library. Limits on the literature search included articles published in the last five years (2014–2019) and written or translated into the English language. Reference lists were reviewed, and sentinel studies identified were included in this review of literature. Excluded from the review of literature were mild and moderate TBI, and non-TBI studies. Literature on cerebrospinal fluid drainage in aneurysmal subarachnoid hemorrhage was later included in the literature review as recommended by the neurosurgery physician champion because of limited studies on CSF drainage in TBI. Research studies addressing the pediatric population were also excluded, as the care of the pediatric population is beyond the author's expertise and scope of practice.

Definition of Terms

For the purposes of this project, the author is providing operational definitions of several terms. Intracranial pressure is the pressure inside the cranium, which normally ranges from 0 to 10 mm Hg (Hickey, 2014). Intracranial hypertension (ICH) is defined as

“ICP > 20 mm Hg for a period of more than 5 minutes” (Boone, Oren-Grinberg, Robinson, Chen, & Kasper, 2015, p. 1). Cerebral perfusion pressure (CPP) is the “blood pressure gradient across the brain” (March & Hickey, 2014, p. 270).

TBI is severe if the score for Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS)—an assessment tool for level of consciousness—falls between a range of 3 to 8 (March & Hickey, 2014). A person whose GCS score falls in this range is comatose and does not perform the following normal physiological functions: eye-opening, following verbal commands, and verbalizing (Stocchetti et al., 2014).

A component of the GCS is assessment of motor response. In comatose patients, the response can range from posturing to no response. Posturing is non-purposeful movement in response to noxious stimuli applied in unconscious patients, which can be either abnormal flexion or abnormal extension (Hickey, 2014). Abnormal flexion (previously known as decorticate positioning) is characterized by “rigidly flexed arms and wrists, fisted hands and extended legs” (Hickey, 2014, p. 174). Abnormal extension (previously known as decerebrate positioning) is characterized by “rigidly, rotated inward extended arms with flexed wrists and fisted hands. The legs are extended” (Hickey, 2014, p. 174).

Adherence

Cnossen et al. (2016) define guideline adherence as “the proportion of patients treated according to a guideline recommendation, which often represents evidence-based or best practice care” (p. 2). Adherence to guidelines in general is low and differs among centers, medical condition, types of guidelines and time-periods. Decreased adherence results in patients not receiving evidence-based care. Results of a systematic review that

examined the relationship between guideline adherence and outcomes in TBI patients revealed a significant association between adherence and reduction in mortality ($OR = 0.15-0.96$; Cnossen et al., 2016).

According to Khormi et al. (2018), factors influencing adherence to BTF guidelines include patient characteristics (age and sex), severity of injury (neurological status and systemic injury), management (decompressive craniectomy/craniotomy), and organizational factors (admission to Level 1 trauma center, higher economic status countries, and health insurance). Furthermore, results of the study by Khormi et al. (2018) showed that the level of adherence was proportionally associated with the strength of evidence. Level I evidence recommendations were associated with optimal adherence, Level II with reasonable adherence, and Level III with suboptimal adherence. ICP monitoring is a Level II evidence recommendation, and CSF drainage is a Level III evidence recommendation (BTF, 2016).

The SIBICC Algorithm

The SIBICC algorithm identified 18 interventions for the management of adult sTBI patients. This new algorithm also identified 10 commonly employed treatments no longer recommended for practice (evidence is lacking). The algorithm used a tiered approach, starting with Tier 0 to establish a stable, neuroprotective baseline regardless of ICP values. Tiers 1–3 guide ICP-based treatments to manage the sTBI patient with established ICH. As the tiers advance, the intensity and aggressiveness of the interventions increase. The sections that follow describe the specific aspects of care identified within Tiers 1–3 of the SIBICC algorithm and the evidence supporting each of the identified interventions selected for discussion.

ICP Monitoring

ICP is monitored invasively by different devices, the gold standard being the EVD. The EVD, previously known as *ventriculostomy*, is placed in the lateral ventricle of the brain through a Burr hole made in the skull (March & Hickey, 2014). The EVD also allows CSF drainage when indicated.

ICP monitoring is a cornerstone in the management of sTBI (BTF, 2016). The use of ICP monitoring to guide therapy is a Level IIB recommendation according to BTF guidelines. However, the indications for ICP monitoring are not formally recommended in the fourth edition due to lack of available evidence supporting the requirements of a Level II/III recommendation. The indications for ICP monitoring include (a) sTBI and an abnormal computed tomography (CT) scan, or (b) sTBI with a normal CT scan with two or more of the following features on admission: age over 40 years, unilateral or bilateral motor posturing, or systolic blood pressure of less than 90 mmHg (BTF, 2016).

Based on the BTF guideline for ICP thresholds (Level IIB recommendation), treating ICP above 22 mm Hg is recommended because of increased mortality associated with ICP levels above 22 mmHg (2016). Results of neuroimaging studies conducted by Honda et al. (2017), however, suggested that an ICP greater than 20 mm Hg is the threshold for initiating treatments for sTBI due to the cerebral circulation disturbance seen at ICP readings beyond this value.

Compliance with the BTF guideline on ICP monitoring is variable because of conflicting research. Several studies show that ICP monitoring is associated with decreased mortality (Agrawal, Raghavendran, Schaubel, Mishra, & Rajajee, 2016; Dawes et al., 2015; MacLaughlin et al., 2015; Shen et al., 2016; You et al., 2016; Yuan et al.,

2016; Yuan et al., 2015). In contrast, one study indicated that ICP monitoring is an independent risk factor for mortality, along with age greater than 65 and increased severity of injury (Piccinini et al., 2017). The conflicting literature has had an impact on decision-making for trauma teams. However, there are ample data that support ICP monitoring, both in quantity of studies and quality of the body of evidence.

Misinterpretation of guidelines may also influence provider adherence. In a study by Hirschi, Rommel, Letsinger, Nirula, and Hawryluk (2018), 36% of physician respondents claimed that they always followed BTF guidelines for ICP monitoring despite the fact that they placed intraparenchymal monitors instead of EVDs—the ICP monitoring device recommended by the BTF.

Cerebrospinal Fluid Drainage

Drainage of CSF is an ICP reduction strategy in the management of sTBI and is included in the BTF guidelines as a Level III evidence recommendation (BTF, 2016). The use of the EVD not only to monitor ICP but also to drain CSF was explored by Liu et al. (2015). The results of their research that compared the EVD to the intraparenchymal monitor demonstrated fewer episodes of refractory ICP in the EVD group when using the intermittent drainage approach, and the benefit of CSF drainage that offset the complications associated with EVDs.

There is limited research concerning CSF drainage in the management of TBI. The study published by Lele et al. (2019) showed that ICP monitoring without CSF drainage within 72 hours of admission was associated with decreased inpatient mortality. In a study by Akbik, Krasberg, Nemoto, and Yonas (2017), however, ICP, CPP, and brain tissue oxygenation (PbtO₂) improved when CSF was drained at ICP values of

greater than 25 mm Hg. ICP decreased by 5.7 (+/- 0.6) mm Hg during the 4 minutes of an opened EVD (Akbik et al., 2017). The results of these two studies appear to be conflicting, but they actually complement each other. Lele et al. (2019) explain that the patients who benefitted from ICP monitoring without CSF drainage were sTBI patients without cerebral edema and intraventricular hemorrhage (Lele et al., 2019).

There is conflicting evidence on the method of CSF drainage. The American College of Surgeons Trauma Quality Improvement Program (2015) advocates for intermittent drainage, a drainage method in which the EVD is kept closed and only opened to drain for a short amount of time necessary to reduce the ICP. However, there is no strong evidence that supports this approach. The BTF recommends continuous CSF drainage which is considered more effective than intermittent drainage (BTF, 2016), but this recommendation is only Level III evidence. Chung et al. (2019) point out that the reason for using continuous CSF drainage is a potentially diminished need for hyperosmolar therapy, which can later be implemented as a rescue intervention.

The only randomized controlled trial (RCT) that compared intermittent to continuous CSF drainage was conducted in patients with subarachnoid hemorrhage (SAH), and found intermittent CSF drainage resulted in fewer EVD complications such as ventriculitis and EVD malfunction (Olson et al., 2013). Ironically, results of a survey of international and US neurointensive care units indicated that majority of these institutions employ the continuous CSF drainage approach and gradual EVD wean despite current evidence of fewer EVD-associated complications with the intermittent method of CSF drainage (Chung, Leslie-Mazwi, Patel, & Rordorf, 2016; Olson, Batjer, Abdulkadir, & Hall, 2014).

Embedded in the SIBICC algorithm is CSF drainage standards, which is an intervention in Tier 1 of the SIBICC algorithm. Although CSF drainage is used as a strategy to reduce elevated ICP, no established practice standards and/or guidelines on CSF drainage had been published. Focusing on specific aspects of CSF drainage that remain unstandardized and left to individual interpretation and clinical judgment (resulting in practice variation among ICU nurses), a critical review of available literature on CSF drainage was performed. A promising study by Candanedo et al. (2019) exploring the topic of the pressure equalization ratio was recently published, and the procedures followed in this novel study served as the basis in the development of the ICP-guided CSF drainage protocol in this DNP project.

Another aspect of CSF drainage that needs to be considered is the issue of how the EVD is weaned once the decision is made to discontinue its use. The rapid wean is described as immediately clamping or closing the EVD once its discontinuation is ordered, while gradual wean involves sequentially raising the height or pressure setting of the EVD system over several days while keeping it open until it is finally clamped (Chung, Mayer, & Rordorf, 2018). Again, there is a lack of evidence for TBI, but several studies exist for SAH patients. Results of an RCT comparing the two methods of weaning EVDs in patients with aneurysmal SAH showed that patients who underwent the gradual wean approach spent a mean of 2.8 more days in the ICU ($p = 0.0002$) and 2.4 more days in the hospital ($p = 0.0314$) than patients who were rapidly weaned (Klopfenstein et al., 2004). This suggests that the rapid wean strategy can decrease EVD, ICU, and hospital days without adverse effects on safety, delayed ischemia, or clinical outcome (Chung et al., 2018).

A more recent review on the management of EVDs focused on patients with TBI, aneurysmal SAH, and intracerebral hemorrhage with intraventricular extension (ICH/IVH). The researchers concluded that both continuous and intermittent CSF drainage methods, as well as rapid and gradual EVD weaning strategies, are reasonable in the management of EVDs in TBI, SAH, and ICH/IVH. However, they found no compelling data to support a recommendation to follow either approach to drain CSF or wean the EVD (Chung et al., 2019).

Hyperosmolar Therapy

Hyperosmolar therapy in the form of mannitol or hypertonic saline (HTS) is employed in the management of ICH and herniation syndromes. They both have a similar mechanism of action of decreasing blood viscosity, which results in increased microcirculation and constriction of pial arterioles and further leads to decreased cerebral blood volume and decreased ICP (BTF, 2016). Hyponatremia, however, is a contraindication for administration of HTS and hypotension is a contraindication for mannitol administration.

Mannitol

In the updated BTF guidelines (fourth edition), the previously recommended guidelines for hyperosmolar therapy are modified to “increase recognition” but not “formally recommended” (the strongest level of evidence). These restated recommendations include (a) administration of mannitol for ICP control at doses of 0.25 g/kg to 1 g/kg body weight while avoiding systolic blood pressure less than 90 mm Hg during infusion and (b) restricted use of mannitol before ICP monitoring to patients with signs of transtentorial herniation or progressive neurological deterioration not attributable

to extracranial causes (BTF, 2016). Because of the osmotic-diuretic effect of mannitol, hypotension as a side effect may be worsened with preexisting or underlying hypotensive condition.

Hypertonic Saline

When given as a bolus and as repeated doses, HTS induces hypernatremia, leading to decreased cell and cerebral blood volume and, eventually, decreased cerebral edema. It also modulates neuro-inflammatory pathways, restores membrane potentials of neurons, and reduces blood viscosity (Hoffman, Jalal, & Chin, 2018). In comparison to the effects of mannitol administration, results of a study involving sTBI patients with ICH revealed that HTS administered as a bolus was demonstrated to be more effective in reducing daily and cumulative ICP and resulted in significantly lower number of ICU days (Mangat et al., 2015). In patients with ICH, a more intense therapy is recommended if HTS fails to result in decreased ICP early in the course of treatment, which is two hours after HTS administration (Colton, et al., 2014). Results of a systematic review of randomized controlled trials comparing HTS and mannitol in the management of sTBI revealed fewer ICP treatment failures with HTS (Burgess, Abu-Laban, Slavik, Vu, & Zed, 2016).

In contrast, another study showed that administration of HTS is no more effective than mannitol in controlling ICP due to increased urinary sodium loss (Jagannatha, Sriganesh, Devi, & Rao, 2018). When administered as a continuous infusion, the use of HTS resulted in significantly higher rates of hyperchloremia and acute kidney injury despite its association with a higher percentage of patients reaching goal osmolality (Maguigan, Denis, Hamblin, & Guillaumondegui, 2017). Therefore, HTS administered as

a continuous infusion is not recommended in the SIBICC algorithm; it is, however, recommended when administered in bolus doses (Hawryluk, et al., 2019).

High-Dose Barbiturates

High-dose barbiturate administration (known also as barbiturate coma) and decompressive craniectomy (DC) are not commonly employed (Lenstra, Van Der Naalt, Coers, & Jacobs, 2017) but are considered for a subset of sTBI patients who have refractory ICH and do not respond to standard medical treatment (BTF, 2016).

Barbiturates decrease ICP by preventing unnecessary movements, coughing, and straining that further increase ICP, and by suppressing cerebral metabolism and altering cerebral vascular tone (BTF, 2016). Dash and Chavali (2018) further explained that sedative agents can decrease metabolic stress (which is an adrenocortical response that results in increased blood pressure and ICP) by reducing cerebral metabolism and consumption of oxygen in a dose-dependent approach. It is critical to maintain hemodynamic stability before and during the administration of high-dose barbiturates. This treatment modality is one of the therapies that are identified in the SIBICC algorithm and listed as a Tier 3 intervention.

Summary

In summary, the quality of evidence supporting individual BTF guidelines varies. ICP monitoring has Level IIB evidence and CSF drainage has Level III evidence (both considered low quality evidence) (BTF, 2016). Literature suggests that adherence rates to guidelines vary according to the strength of the evidence supporting the standards (Khormi et al., 2018). Carney et al. (2016) advocated for development of treatment protocols based on consensus and clinical judgement, especially in areas that currently

lack strong evidence. The SIBICC task force operationalized the BTF guidelines into the SIBICC algorithm which guided this quality improvement project to improve ICP monitoring and CSF drainage in patients with sTBI.

METHODS

The purpose of this DNP project was to increase adherence to the BTF's guidelines for ICP monitoring and CSF drainage during the first 24 hours after EVD placement in patients with sTBI. The objectives of this project were to (a) describe baseline adherence rates to ICP monitoring and CSF drainage during the first 24 hours after EVD placement in a sample of six adult sTBI patients cared for from January to March 2020, (b) develop and implement ICP monitoring guidelines and a CSF drainage protocol, (c) develop and implement an educational program regarding the SIBICC algorithm and CSF drainage protocol for ICP management, and (d) evaluate adherence to the BTF guidelines for ICP monitoring and CSF drainage in a similar sample of six patients with sTBI, (e) increase nurse knowledge related to BTF guidelines on ICP monitoring and CSF drainage, and (f) increase self-efficacy of ICP monitoring and CSF drainage.

Due to COVID-19, the author was unable to implement and evaluate the use of the SIBICC algorithm and CSF drainage protocol for ICP management during this DNP project. Thus, these two stages will be completed at a future date; however, the proposed evaluation plan will be discussed in this paper.

Design and Samples

A quality improvement approach was used to address the aims of this project. A convenience sample of six patients pre implementation was selected who met the following inclusion criteria: (a) age 18 years and over with an EVD, (b) diagnosis of sTBI, and (c) admission to the surgical-trauma ICU within 24 hours of arrival to the emergency department. Trauma-based criteria for placement of EVDs for ICP monitoring

at the project setting are (a) GCS of 4–8 after resuscitation, (b) non-futile condition per neurosurgery, and (c) either an abnormal CT scan or a normal CT scan with two or more of the following features on admission: age over 40 years, unilateral or bilateral motor posturing, or systolic blood pressure of less than 90 mmHg. Patients diagnosed with brain death within 24 hours of ICU admission were excluded from the sample pool of six patients. A convenience sample of ICU nurses was surveyed to evaluate knowledge of and confidence with ICP monitoring and CSF drainage before and after education.

Measures

Six outcomes were identified for this DNP project: (a) completeness of ICP monitoring, (b) ICP monitoring adherence rate, (c) completeness of CSF drainage, (d) CSF drainage adherence rate, (e) knowledge of BTF guidelines on ICP monitoring and CSF drainage, and (f) self-efficacy on ICP monitoring and CSF drainage. Although measurement of adherence to each component of the BTF guidelines is possible, for brevity and the purposes of this DNP project, the author chose to measure only the adherence rates to BTF guidelines for ICP monitoring and CSF drainage.

Ethical Considerations

The institution's setting provided institutional review board (IRB) approval (see Appendix J). Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act compliance, data security, and data storage methods were approved. Data were recorded in an Excel file stored in an institutionally secured and managed network drive accessible only to the author and two nursing policy administrators to protect patient privacy and confidentiality. A separate data file was maintained in a password-protected computer that linked the patient's medical record number with the subject identification number.

Information from this file was also documented manually in a notebook kept secure in a locked cabinet in the author's office only accessible to the author.

Procedures

After IRB approval, baseline data were collected from the EHR from a convenience sample of six sTBI patients meeting inclusion and exclusion criteria for the period of January to March 2020. Age, gender, ethnicity as well as clinical information including initial GCS, GCS after resuscitation, date and time of ED arrival, date and time of ICU admission, history of trauma, initial head CT results, systolic blood pressure prior to EVD placement, unilateral or bilateral posturing prior to EVD placement, ICP values, volumes of CSF drained, and method of CSF drainage were abstracted from the electronic health record.

Education

All ICU registered nurses were included in the education. To ensure consistency, the author developed a standardized curriculum related to the SIBICC algorithm and the CSF drainage protocol (See Appendices C and D). The educational training covered an introduction to TBI, BTF guidelines, and the SIBICC algorithm's tiered approach to TBI management. The 30-minute educational sessions highlighted practice changes associated with the SIBICC algorithm and explained the process of draining CSF. The author also developed a case study to apply concepts learned (See Appendix C). The physician champions, the trauma division chief and neurosurgery attending physician, provided the education to the medical staff in the trauma and neurosurgery services.

Data Analysis

Outcomes were evaluated as follows:

1. Completeness of ICP monitoring in a sample of six pre- and six post-implementation patients
 - a. Numerator – Number of ICP values entered within the first 24 hours after the EVD placement in sTBI patients who meet criteria for ICP monitoring
 - b. Denominator – Total number of hourly ICP values per ICP monitoring protocol plus the number of intermittent CSF drainage events per the CSF drainage protocol
2. Adherence to BTF guideline for ICP monitoring in a sample of six pre- and six post- implementation patients
 - a. Numerator – Number of sTBI patients with complete data on ICP monitoring
 - b. Denominator – Total number of sTBI patients on ICP monitoring
3. Completeness of CSF drainage measurement in a sample of six pre- and post-implementation patients
 - a. Numerator – Number of recorded CSF drainage events
 - b. Denominator – Total Number of ICP values greater than 20 mm Hg sustained for five minutes or more (meeting criteria for CSF drainage)
4. Adherence to BTF guideline on CSF drainage
 - a. Numerator – Number of sTBI patients with complete data on CSF drainage
 - b. Denominator – Total number of sTBI patients on ICP monitoring
5. Knowledge of the CSF drainage protocol and the BTF guidelines related to ICP monitoring
 - a. An author generated multiple-choice questionnaire (based on the literature and clinician experience) assessed nurses' knowledge of the CSF drainage protocol and ICP monitoring (see Appendix K). An example of a question is "For intermittent CSF drainage, ICP and CPP are to be monitored and documented: a) every hour, b) every hour and before CSF drainage, c) every hour and after CSF drainage, and d) every hour, before and after CSF drainage." Correct answers of the six questions were summed for a total correct score (range 0–6) and compared pre-education and post-education.

6. Self-efficacy on ICP monitoring and CSF drainage
 - a. The author generated a 2-item Likert scale survey assessing self-efficacy (confidence) with ICP monitoring and CSF drainage (see Appendix K). Responses vary from not confident to extremely confident (1-5). Each question was reported separately. Scores were compared pre-education and post-education.

RESULTS

In this section, characteristics of the patient sample are described. Baseline data on documentation completeness and adherence rates of ICP monitoring and CSF drainage are presented as well as outcomes related to the BTF guideline educational process.

Patient Characteristics

There were three males and three females in the patient sample. Ages ranged from 50 to 72 years (mean 60.17, standard deviation 8.23). Glasgow coma scale scores varied, with 3/15 in 5 patients, and 8/15 in one patient.

Completeness of Documentation and Adherence Rates

Documentation completeness for ICP monitoring varied from 59% to 100% with a mean of 83%. CSF drainage documentation completeness varied from 28% to 80% with a mean of 65.3% (see Tables 1 and 2). Baseline guideline adherence rates to ICP monitoring was 33% and 0% for CSF drainage (see Table 3).

Table 1

Completeness of Documentation for ICP Monitoring Pre-Implementation

Patient	Number of documented ICP entries	Total number of ICP entries	Completeness of documentation (%)
1	39	52	75
2	24	25	96
3	25	25	100
4	68	115	59
5	49	49	100
6	17	25	68
Average			83

Table 2

Completeness of Documentation for CSF Drainage Pre-Implementation

Patient	Number of documented CSF entries	Total number of CSF entries	Completeness of documentation (%)
1	20	25	80
2	7	25	28
3	19	25	76
4	17	25	68
5	18	25	72
6	17	25	68
Average			65.3

Table 3

Adherence Rates to BTF Guidelines Pre-Implementation

Sample	ICP monitoring <i>n</i> (%)	CSF drainage <i>n</i> (%)
Pre-Implementation (<i>N</i> = 6)	2 (33)	0 (0)

Education

A total of 61 nurses participated in the educational sessions. Fifty-three completed the pre-test, and 61 completed the post-test. At baseline, nurses were least likely to identify indications for continuous CSF drainage (15% provided a correct response). Questions related to switching from intermittent to continuous methods of CSF drainage and EVD placement criteria showed the greatest improvement with education (46.3% improvement and 44.6 % improvement respectively; Table 4). Nurses were least likely to improve in their knowledge of indications for intermittent CSF drainage methods (knowledge decreased 3.8 percentage points). The knowledge score improved from an

average of 55.6% at baseline to 80% post-education (Table 4). The distribution of the knowledge scores are reflected in Figure 2, which compares the knowledge scores on ICP monitoring and CSF drainage before education (pre-test) and after education (post-test).

Table 4

Knowledge of ICP Monitoring and CSF Drainage: Pre-Post Score Item Analysis

Item number	Item Topic	% Correct pre-test (N = 53)	% Correct post-test (N = 61)	% Point Rate of change
1	EVD placement criteria	28.3	72.1	44.6
2	Indication for intermittent method of CSF drainage	90.6	86.8	-3.8
3	ICP monitoring and documentation for intermittent method	67.9	91.8	23.9
4	Switching from intermittent to continuous method of CSF drainage	47.1	93.4	46.3
5	Indication for continuous method of CSF drainage	15	42.6	27.6
6	Maximum volume of CSF drainage	84.9	93.4	13.5
Average Score		55.6%	80%	26.6%

Nurses' self-efficacy of ICP monitoring improved from 12% to 17% for the highly confident item. This improvement corresponded to a reduction for the not confident item from 12% to 0% (see Table 5). Figure 3 illustrates self-efficacy of ICP monitoring pre and post-test in a column chart format. It shows the results of the survey assessing the nurses' self-efficacy or confidence in their ability to conduct ICP monitoring. A 5-point Likert scale was used with the range of response choices from not confident to extremely confident.

Figure 2. Pre- and post-test knowledge scores.

Figure 3 displays the results of the survey assessing the nurses' self-efficacy or confidence in ICP monitoring using the 5-point Likert scale (ranges from not confident to extremely confident).

Table 5

Self-Efficacy (Confidence) on ICP Monitoring

	Not confident 1 <i>n</i> (%)	Somewhat confident 2 <i>n</i> (%)	Confident 3 <i>n</i> (%)	Highly confident 4 <i>n</i> (%)	Extremely confident 5 <i>n</i> (%)
Pre-test (<i>N</i> = 43)	5 (12)	10 (23)	18 (42)	5 (12)	5 (12)
Post-test (<i>N</i> = 61)	0 (0)	13 (25)	17 (33)	9 (17)	7 (14)

Figure 3. Self-Efficacy on ICP monitoring.

Nurses' self-efficacy of CSF drainage also improved from 7% to 20% for the highly confident item. This increase in self-efficacy corresponded to a decrease in the not confident item from 12% to 0% (see Table 6). Figure 4 illustrates self-efficacy on CSF drainage in a column chart. This column chart shows the results of the survey assessing the nurses' self-efficacy or confidence in CSF drainage using the 5-point Likert scale (ranges from not confident to extremely confident).

Table 6

Self-Efficacy (Confidence) on CSF Drainage

	Not confident 1 <i>n</i> (%)	Somewhat confident 2 <i>n</i> (%)	Confident 3 <i>n</i> (%)	Highly confident 4 <i>n</i> (%)	Extremely confident 5 <i>n</i> (%)
Pre-test (<i>N</i> = 43)	5 (12)	13 (31)	16 (38)	3 (7)	6 (12)
Post-test (<i>N</i> = 61)	0 (0)	13 (28)	18 (39)	9 (20)	6 (13)

Figure 4. Self-efficacy on CSF drainage.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this project was to improve adherence to BTF guidelines on ICP monitoring and CSF drainage. While the author was not able to complete the project due to COVID-19, valuable lessons were learned in terms of evidence-based practice (EBP), practice variation, and interprofessional collaboration.

Evidence-Based Practice

All quality improvement activities should be based on relevant literature, clinician experience (or, in this case, the institutional culture/setting), and patient preferences. While patient preferences were not relevant to this project, the QI project was built upon an extensive literature review and the preferences of the stakeholders and institution. EBP is the cornerstone of the sixth DNP essential (American Association of Colleges of Nursing, 2016) and is defined as “the process by which healthcare providers incorporate the best research or evidence into clinical practice in combination with clinical expertise and within the context of patient values” (Franz & Cataldo, 2013, p. 1285). Both the SIBICC algorithm created by an international group of experts and the CSF drainage protocol developed by a local group composed of the author and neurosurgery and trauma attending physicians were based on the best available research evidence and collective clinical expertise. Implementation of the SIBICC algorithm and the CSF drainage protocol illustrates the application and translation of best evidence into practice.

Although EBP strongly considers clinician experience, application of EBP requires bedside nurses to abandon old habits and embrace the practice change. Implementing practice changes and sustaining a culture of EBP are two EBP

competencies identified in the scope and standards of practice for acute and critical care nurses established by the American Association of Critical-Care Nurses (AACN, 2015).

Variation in Practice

A national practice survey by Olson et al. (2014) and a literature review by Chung et al. (2019) found similar variations or inconsistencies in monitoring and documenting ICP. Some nurses documented at 30-minute intervals, others at 60-minute intervals. The project author found it difficult to ascertain from the medical records of the six baseline patients whether changes in ICP values followed specific interventions. For the planned practice change at the author's setting, ICP readings before and after CSF drain will be documented. Additionally, hourly ICP readings at the end/beginning of the hour will be the standard of care. The ICP will be continuously monitored but only documented when warranted as indicated in the protocol. Adherence to the CSF drainage protocol will provide a clearer picture of the sTBI patient's dynamic brain physiology for clinicians.

Evaluation of documentation of CSF drainage pre-implementation also revealed practice variation. Currently, duration of CSF drainage varies from one ICU nurse to another when the intermittent method is used (because of the absence of procedural guidance in this area). It is interesting to note that the item assessing knowledge of intermittent CSF drainage demonstrated the least improvement of all the knowledge questions (knowledge decreased 3.8 percentage points). For some nurses, CSF drainage means allowing a self-determined number of CSF drops in the drainage chamber to fall and closing the EVD immediately thereafter to check the ICP. For others, CSF drainage means opening the EVD to drain over a self-determined duration of time that ranges from

seconds to minutes. The CSF drainage protocol clarifies and establishes this duration as the time it takes until CSF stops to drain.

Unwarranted variation in clinical practice is defined as “variation that is not explained on the basis of illness, patient risk factors or patient preferences” (Corallo et al., 2014, p. 6). Described another way, unwarranted practice variation (UPV) is defined as “variation that cannot be explained by the condition or preference of the patient; it is variation that can only be explained by differences in health system performance” (Agency for Clinical Innovation, 2017, para. 1). The deleterious effects of practice variation are barriers to equitable health care and provision of evidence-based treatment to all patients (Australian Commission on Safety and Quality in Health Care, 2017). Harrison et al. (2019) suggest that existence of UPV indicates inconsistency in adherence to evidence-based guidelines. According to Cook et al. (2019), care algorithms reduce practice variation, and establishing the SIBICC algorithm and CSF drainage protocol will address this issue and potentially increase adherence to the BTF guidelines, which is the main purpose of this project.

Interprofessional Collaboration

This quality improvement project was a result of collaborative team effort among neurosurgery, trauma, and nursing. As a clinical nurse specialist working closely with physician leaders in the hospital setting, the author was in a unique position to collaborate with the attending physicians and other members of the project team. Collaboration, or working in interprofessional teams, is valued by the National CNS Task Force as well as the Institute of Medicine (Finkelman, 2013). Due to the nature and demands of the trauma and neurosurgery services, establishing meeting times with the surgeons posed

huge challenges. Despite these challenges, communication among disciplines was maintained and a complex project was integrated across medicine and nursing.

Limitations

There are several limitations to this quality improvement project, and the most significant of these is the inability to reach full implementation within the specified timeframe. Given the evolving nature of EBP, it took a significant amount of time to adopt the SIBICC algorithm. The project author, together with the neurosurgery and trauma attending physicians, were developing an ICP-guided protocol based on the BTF guidelines when the SIBICC algorithm was published. Completion of the project was further delayed by the full IRB review process. Lastly, the occurrence of the COVID-19 pandemic abruptly halted the education, which was a crucial component of the project. In terms of the quality improvement process, six data points on ICP monitoring and CSF drainage (pre- and post-implementation) are not sufficient to adequately evaluate the efficacy of the practice change (Langley et al., 2009). Despite these limitations, this project enabled the author to examine the gap between current practice and EBP. The author plans to mentor the nursing staff through the practice change and lead efforts to ensure sustainability.

Conclusion

In conclusion, completeness of documentation and adherence rates for both ICP monitoring and CSF drainage is less than optimal at the project setting. Inconsistencies in the documentation for ICP monitoring and CSF drainage exist and present a target for practice improvement and, ultimately, improving patient outcomes. As this paper goes to

press, the author continues her work of improving sTBI patient care to mitigate the substantial sequelae of this devastating condition for her patients and their families.

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APPENDIX A

CLASS FLYER

Department of Nursing presents

Seattle International Traumatic Brain Injury Consensus Conference (SIBICC) Algorithm and Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF) Drainage Protocol

Speaker:

Susan Ulit, MSN, RN, CCRN-K, CNRN, SCRN
Clinical Nurse Specialist, Critical/Progressive Care Services

This class will provide an overview of severe traumatic brain injury and its management utilizing the SIBICC algorithm based on the Brain Trauma Foundation (BTF) guidelines and current evidence. The class focuses on the CSF drainage protocol, an evidence-based set of guidelines HUCLA will be using in the very near future that describes when to drain CSF via the external ventricular drain (EVD), the two methods of CSF drainage, and the associated monitoring and documentation of intracranial pressure.

March 10-12, 2020 Tuesday-Thursday 0730-0800 2E-4	March 13, 2020 Friday 0730-0800 2E-2	March 14, 2020 Saturday 0730-0800 6L-2	March 16, 2020 Monday 0730-0800 2E-1
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*Upon successful completion, participants are eligible for 0.5 contact hours of continuing education credit.
 Provider approved by the California Board of Registered Nursing provider number 13638.*

APPENDIX B
CLASS SCHEDULE

TIME	TOPIC	DURATION
0730-0735	Introduction	2 minutes
0735-0743	SIBICC Algorithm	8 minutes
0743-0748	ICP Monitoring	5 minutes
0748-0756	CSF Drainage Protocol	8 minutes
0756-0758	Case Study	2 minutes
0758-0800	Question and Answer	2 minutes

APPENDIX C
CLASS OUTLINE

- I. Introduction
 - A. Definition of TBI
 - B. Cost of TBI
 - C. Adherence to Brain Trauma Foundation (BTF) Guidelines on Severe TBI

- II. Seattle International Severe Traumatic Brain Injury Consensus Conference (SIBICC) Algorithm

- III. ICP Monitoring
 - A. Criteria for EVD Placement
 - 1. Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) score of 4-8 after resuscitation
 - 2. Computerized Tomography (CT) scan results (one of the two)
 - a. Abnormal CT scan results
 - i. Hematomas
 - ii. Concussions
 - iii. Swelling
 - iv. Compressed basal cisterns
 - b. Normal CT scan results with two or more of the following:
 - i. Age over 40 years
 - ii. Unilateral or bilateral posturing
 - iii. Systolic blood pressure < 90 mm Hg
 - B. ICP Monitoring Protocol
 - 1. Monitor ICP and CPP
 - a. At the end of the hour
 - b. Before CSF drainage
 - c. After CSF drainage

- IV. CSF Drainage
 - A. Criteria for CSF Drainage: ICP > 20 mm Hg sustained for > 5 minutes
 - B. CSF Drainage Protocol
 - 1. Intermittent CSF Drainage
 - a. Record the ICP and CPP before CSF drainage
 - b. Drain CSF by opening the EVD until CSF stops to drain, then return to monitoring (closed) position
 - c. Record the ICP and immediately after CSF drainage when ICP reading stabilizes and stops to fluctuate

- d. If intermittent drainage is required three or more times consecutively within the hour, switch to continuous CSF drainage
2. Continuous CSF Drainage
 - a. Open the EVD to drain
 - b. Record the ICP and CPP at the end of the hour
3. Do not exceed the maximum hourly CSF drainage of 25 mL/hour

V. Case Study

A 75-year-old man is brought in to the emergency department after a witnessed ground level fall from home. He had a GCS score of 3 in the field and intubated on route to the hospital. Head CT scan results show a subdural hematoma at the left parietal lobe. The GCS remains unchanged after resuscitation in the ED and an EVD is placed immediately upon admission to the ICU at 0800, and had an initial ICP of 18 mm Hg.

- A. It is now 0815 and the ICP monitor shows 24 mm Hg, and ICP still shows 25 mmHg at 0820. Based on the CSF drainage protocol, what CSF drainage method should be used? How long will you drain CSF or how much CSF are you to drain? When do you document ICP and CPP?
- B. At 0840, the ICP alarm rings, and at 0846, ICP is at 26 mm Hg. Based on the CSF drainage protocol, what CSF drainage method should be used? How long will you drain CSF or how much CSF are you to drain? When do you document ICP and CPP?
- C. At 0850, the ICP climbs up to 28 mm Hg, and remains elevated at 27 mmHg at 0857. Based on the CSF drainage protocol, what CSF drainage method should be used? When do you document ICP and CPP? What other actions need to be taken?

APPENDIX D
SIBICC ALGORITHM

APPENDIX E

TIERED INTERVENTIONS IN SIBICC ALGORITHM

Tier 0 Interventions

EVD Placement
 ICU Admission
 Endotracheal intubation and mechanical ventilation
 Serial evaluation of neuro status and pupillary reactivity
 HOB elevation 30-40°
 Analgesia for pain management
 Sedation to prevent agitation, vent asynchrony
 Temperature management to prevent fever
 Central line insertion
 End-tidal CO₂ monitoring
 Maintain CPP \geq 60 mm Hg
 Maintain Hb $>$ 7 g/dL
 Maintain SpO₂ \geq 94%
 Consider anti-seizure prophylaxis for 7 days only
 Avoid hyponatremia
 Optimize venous return from head (keep head midline, ensure collar not too tight)

Tier 1 Interventions

Increase analgesia to lower ICP
 Increase sedation to lower ICP
 Maintain CPP @ 60-70 mm Hg
 Maintain pCO₂ @ 35-38 mm Hg
 Mannitol by intermittent bolus
 Hypertonic saline by intermittent bolus
 CSF drainage
 Consider EVD placement if intraparenchymal probe used
 Consider EEG monitoring

Tier 2 Interventions

Maintain pCO₂ @ 32-35 mm Hg
 Neuromuscular blocking agent trial dose in adequately sedated patients
 Consider MAP challenge
 Consider increasing CPP with fluid boluses, vasopressors and/or inotropes when autoregulation is intact

Tier 3 Interventions

Secondary decompressive craniectomy
 Pentobarbital Coma
 Mild hypothermia (35-36°C)

APPENDIX F**TREATMENTS THAT ARE NOT RECOMMENDED
AND EVD PLACEMENT CRITERIA****TREATMENTS THAT ARE NOT RECOMMENDED**

Mannitol by non-bolus continuous infusion
Scheduled infusion of hyperosmolar therapy
Lumbar CSF drainage
Furosemide
Routine use of steroids
Routine use of TTM to temp < 35
High-dose propofol to burst suppression
Routine decrease of pCO₂ < 30
Routinely raising CPP > 90 mm Hg

EVD PLACEMENT CRITERIA

GCS 4-8 after resuscitation AND salvageable per neurosurgery
Abnormal head computerized tomography (CT) OR
Hematomas
Contusions
Swelling
Herniation
Compressed basal cisterns
Normal CT with \geq two of the following:
Age over 40 years old
Posturing
Systolic blood pressure < 90 mm Hg

APPENDIX G

CRITICAL NEUROWORSENING AND RESPONSE

CRITICAL NEUROWORSENING

A serious deterioration in clinical neurologic status such as:

- Spontaneous decrease in the GCS motor score of ≥ 1 points (compared with the previous examination)
- New decrease in pupillary reactivity
- New pupillary asymmetry or bilateral mydriasis
- New focal motor deficit
- Herniation syndrome or Cushing's Triad which requires an immediate physician response

RESPONSE TO CRITICAL NEUROWORSENING

Emergent evaluation to identify possible cause of neuroworsening which include:

- Expanding intracranial mass lesion
- Cerebral edema
- Elevated ICP
- Stroke
- Electrolyte or other metabolic disturbance
- Medical comorbidity
- Medication effect
- Impaired renal or hepatic function
- Systemic hypotension
- Seizure or post-ictal state
- Hypoxemia/tissue hypoxia
- CNS infection
- Infection or sepsis

If herniation is suspected:

- Empiric treatment
- Hyperventilation (hyperventilation pCO₂ limit does not apply here)
- Bolus of hypertonic saline
- Consider emergent imaging or other testing
- Rapid escalation of treatment

APPENDIX H
CSF DRAINAGE PROTOCOL

ICP (mm Hg)	CSF drainage method	When to monitor and record ICP and CPP
0-20	No drainage	End of hour
21-29	Intermittent	Pre-drain, post-drain, and end of hour
≥ 30 OR ≥ 3 consecutive intermittent drains within an hour	Continuous	End of hour

- For intermittent CSF drainage:
 - Record the ICP and CPP before CSF drain
 - Open the EVD until CSF stops to drain
 - Record the ICP and CPP immediately after CSF drain (when ICP reading stabilizes and stops to fluctuate)
 - If intermittent drainage is required three or more times consecutively within an hour, switch to continuous CSF drain (open to drain)
 - Notify the MD at initiation of intermittent drainage and when switching from intermittent to continuous CSF drainage
- Do NOT exceed max CSF drainage of 25 mL/hour

APPENDIX I
LEARNING OUTCOMES

Upon completion of the educational session, the participants will be able to:

Cognitive Domain:

- 1) Describe the tiered approach of the SIBICC algorithm
- 2) Differentiate between intermittent and continuous CSF drainage and discuss when each of these methods are indicated based on the CSF drainage protocol
- 3) Discuss when ICP and CPP are monitored for both intermittent and continuous CSF drainage methods

Affective Domain:

- 1) Explain the importance of adhering to BTF guidelines

APPENDIX J

IRB APPROVAL LETTER

COMPLIANCE OFFICE
 John F. Wolf, M.D. Human Subjects Committee
 IRB@lundquist.org
 p: (310) 222-3624 | f: (310) 782-0486

EXEMPT DETERMINATION

March 10, 2020

██████████
 ██████████

Dear ██████████:

On 03/10/2020, the John F. Wolf, M.D. Human Subjects Committee (1) reviewed the following protocol:

Type of Review/Submission:	Exempt/Initial Review, Reference #050182
Project Title:	Improving Adherence to Brain Trauma Foundation Guidelines on Intracranial Pressure Monitoring and Cerebrospinal Fluid Drainage
Investigator:	██████████
IRB Project No.:	18CR-32063-01
Funding Agency:	None
Documents reviewed:	IRB Pre-Review Correction Form (Version 1.0) Submission Packet for Initial Review (Version 1.0) IRB Application (Version 1.1) DHS Approval Category 2 (Version 1.0) Data Collection Tool (Version 1.1) Adherence to BTF Guidelines Study Protocol Ulit 32063-01 (Version 1.0) ICP-Guided Therapy Algorithm Ulit 32063-01 (Version 1.0) Abbreviated Institutional Research Project Application (Version 1.0) Maria Jesusa Ulit CV (Version 1.0)

The John F. Wolf, M.D. Human Subjects Committee (1) determined that the protocol was Exempt under Exempt Category #4 on 03/10/2020.

In conducting this research, you are required to follow the requirements listed in the INVESTIGATOR MANUAL (HRP-103).

Ongoing IRB review and approval by this organization is not required. This determination applies only to the activities described in the above submission and does not apply should any changes be made. If changes are made and there are questions about whether these activities impact the exempt determination, please submit a new request to the IRB for a determination.

Important Note: Approval by the IRB does not, in and of itself, constitute approval for the implementation of this research. Other clearance and approvals The Lundquist Institute or other external agency or collaborating institutional approvals may be required before study activities and initiated. Research undertaken in conjunction with outside entities, such as drug or device companies, are typically contractual in nature and require an agreement between the institute and the entity.

Sincerely,

LUNDQUIST INSTITUTE FOR BIOMEDICAL INNOVATION AT HARBOR-UCLA MEDICAL CENTER
 ██████████

Exempt Determination (Ref#050182)
Page 2 of 2

IRB Project No. 18CR-32063-01

Signature applied by [REDACTED] CIP on 03/10/2020 01:21:48 PM PDT

[REDACTED] CIP
Compliance Office

cc: Maria Jesusa Ulit, R.N., M.S.N.
Office of Research Administration

APPENDIX K**PRE-TEST AND POST-TEST**

For questions 1-6, circle the letter that corresponds to your answer:

1. EVD placement for ICP monitoring for a severe TBI patient with a normal CT scan includes the following criteria EXCEPT:
 - a. Posturing
 - b. Age over 40
 - c. SBP < 90 mm Hg
 - d. DBP < 60 mm Hg

2. Which of the following is intermittent CSF drainage indicated for?
 - a. ICP > 20 mm Hg and pO₂ < 85 mm Hg
 - b. ICP > 20 mm Hg and pCO₂ > 25 mm Hg
 - c. ICP > 20 mm Hg sustained for 3 minutes or longer
 - d. ICP > 20 mm Hg sustained for 5 minutes or longer

3. For intermittent CSF drainage, ICP and CPP are to be monitored and documented:
 - a. Every hour
 - b. Every hour and before CSF drainage
 - c. Every hour and after CSF drainage
 - d. Every hour, before, and after CSF drainage

4. Intermittent CSF drainage is switched to continuous CSF drainage when:
 - a. 5 or more consecutive intermittent drainage events are performed within the hour
 - b. 3 or more consecutive intermittent drainage events are performed within the hour
 - c. 4 or more consecutive intermittent drainage events are performed within the hour
 - d. 2 or more consecutive intermittent drainage events are performed within the hour

5. Continuous CSF drainage is indicated when ICP is greater than or equal to which ICP value?
 - a. 15 mm Hg
 - b. 20 mm Hg
 - c. 25 mm Hg
 - d. 30 mm Hg

6. The maximum allowable CSF volume that will be drained per hour to avoid hemorrhage is:
 - a. 25 mL/hour
 - b. 30 mL/hour
 - c. 35 mL/hour
 - d. 40 mL/hour

For questions 7-8, using the 5-point rating scale, please circle the response that best corresponds to your level of confidence related to the two areas of nursing care identified below:

7. Interpreting when to monitor and record ICP and CPP

Extremely Confident	Highly Confident	Confident	Somewhat Confident	Not Confident
5	4	3	2	1

8. Following the ICP parameters that define the method of CSF

Extremely Confident	Highly Confident	Confident	Somewhat Confident	Not Confident
5	4	3	2	1